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Role of substitution in mitigating the supply pressure of rare earths in electric road transport applications

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ABSTRACT

The development of new high-efficiency magnets and/or electric traction motors using a limited amount of critical rare earths or none at all is crucial for the large-scale deployment of electric vehicles (EVs) and related applications, such as hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) and e-bikes. For these applications, we estimated the short-term demand for high-performing NdFeB magnets and their constituent rare earths: neodymium, praseodymium and dysprosium. In 2020, EV, HEV and e-bike applications combined could require double the amount used in 2015. To meet the global deployment target of 7.2 million EVs sales in 2020 proposed by the International Energy Agency, the demand for NdFeB in the EV sector might increase by up to 14 times in only 5 years (2015–2020). Due to concerns about the security of supply of rare earths some manufacturers have decided to develop and adopt alternative solutions. By assessing up-to-date available component substitutes, we show that the permanent magnet synchronous-traction motor (PSM) remains the technology of choice, especially for hybrid vehicles (HEV and PHEV). Better material efficiency and a larger adoption of motors free of rare earths have the potential to reduce the pressure on rare earths supply for use in electric road transport applications. However even if such substitution measures are successfully implemented, the demand growth for rare earths in the EV sector is expected to increase significantly by 2020 and beyond.

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1. Introduction

Countries gathered at the 2015 Paris Climate Conference (COP21) agreed to increase their efforts to limit climate change. Transport is a growing sector that contributes almost one-quarter of current global energy-related GHG emissions. More than half of this is related to road passenger transport [1,2]. For example, in Europe, transport accounts for more than 30% of final energy consumption and the European Commission is already taking actions to decarbonise the transport sector [3]. Limiting global temperature increases to below 2 °C requires sustainable transportation solutions. Electromobility for various transport modes coupled with a low-carbon power system is seen as a promising sustainable solution. Electrified road transport is not a new concept, but it is only recently that electric vehicles (EVs) have gained relevant mass-market sales through third-generation technology. Several factors push up the electromobility trend, such as the increasing volatility of oil prices, air quality concerns, climate change agreements, more stringent emission standards and market momentum for EVs. At the end of 2015, the global EV stock accounted for over 1.26 million units and global EV sales in 2015 amounted to over 550,000 cars [4]. Although the number of electric vehicles on the road is still very low when compared to the total number of passenger cars worldwide (0.1%), the shift towards electrified powertrains is becoming more apparent. For instance, in 2015 the share of passenger EVs exceeded 1% of new market sales in Norway, the Netherlands, Sweden, Denmark, France, China and the UK [4].

Several countries have set up ambitious sales and/or stock targets regarding vehicle electrification as guidance for creating national roadmaps and for gathering support from policymakers. Among various uptake scenarios, the International Energy Agency (IEA) and the Electric Vehicles Initiative (EVI), a multi-government policy forum composed today of 16 members, presented an aggregated global deployment target of 7.2 million in annual sales of EVs and 24 million in EVs stock by 2020 [5]. This is an important milestone in meeting the global deployment target of 100 million EVs by 2030 as announced at COP21 in the Paris declaration on electromobility and climate change and call for action [4]. An even more ambitious target (140 million EVs by 2030) is presented by IEA under the 2 °C scenario [4]. For instance in Europe the combined targets aim to reach up to 8–9 million EVs on the road by 2020, but specific targets and timelines are subject to negotiation with the EU's member states [6].

It is important to consider here the impact of availability of material resources and their secure supply on the future deployment pathway of EVs in view of the overall concerns about the supply of certain materials in the global transition to a sustainable energy future [7–10]. In previous studies conducted by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) we showed that several low-carbon energy technologies could be at risk because of potential bottlenecks in the supply chains of certain metals [11–13]. Among these technologies, electric vehicles are of particular concern due to the dependence on critical rare earths used in NdFeB permanent magnets (PM), which are essential for producing light, compact and high efficiency traction motors. Such magnets contain neodymium (Nd), praseodymium (Pr) and dysprosium (Dy) rare earths in their composition. Dysprosium is used as an additive to improve the magnet coercivity at high temperatures [14].

In recent years, traditional asynchronous motors have been continuously replaced by more efficient devices containing permanent magnets, e.g. high efficient PM synchronous-traction motors (PSM) in EVs, HEVs and e-bikes [15]. Due to the high energy density of NdFeB, this magnet is also increasingly used in high-tech applications and energy-related devices such as generators in wind turbines [16,17]. Consequently, it is expected that the global demand for Nd, Pr and Dy elements will increase in the coming years as the market in these sectors will most likely increase [16,18–20].

A series of events, such as imposing export restrictions on rare earth elements (REEs) by the near-monopolist China, caused the supply crisis

from 2010 to 2011 that drove up prices by between 4 and 9 times in less than a year [21–24]. As a result, the costs of products containing rare earths increased. Although prices for rare earths have declined since 2013, concerns regarding the supply of rare earths continue among industry and governments as another supply crisis remains a distinct possibility [16,18]. These supply concerns are also due to the current reorganisation of rare earth market as well as introduction by the Chinese government of various measures to limit REE production, driven by environmental, social and resources preservation aspects.

Based on specific risk assessments, rare earths are in general evaluated as 'critical materials' [25–30]. Different mitigation strategies such as the development of new mines and recycling are being considered, but both are seen as unrealistic to be implemented in the short-term.

From one side many barriers prevent a fast and sustainable primary production and on the other side large volumes of secondary rare earth-based products are not expected to enter soon into the recycling circuit [24,31,32]. In the midst of this is the substitution. A complete and direct (one-by-one) replacement of all critical materials by other more readily available or less critical without decreasing product performance, raise the price or both, is very limited [33]. However, the substitution of rare earths and other critical materials appears to be a feasible solution, especially in cases where the substitution takes place at the product, component or technology level rather than the element level [34–36]. According to Smith and Eggert [36], material substitution has 'multifaceted' dimensions and the authors identify five types of substitution in the case of NdFeB magnet: element-for element, technology-for-element, grade-for-grade, magnet-for magnet and system-for-system substitution. The literature seems to agree on the fact that substitution represents an essential component of the strategy towards a sustainable use of scarce resources or environmentally problematic materials [37–40].

Comprehensive information about the substitution of rare earths in permanent magnets and the impact of this approach on reducing reliance on rare earths in relation to the widespread adoption of electric vehicles is limited in the literature. The state-of-the-art of some rare earths-free propulsion motors was addressed in several reviews [15,41,42]. Here we intend to complement the literature by assessing the current technological status of these components and offer an outlook on further developments. We are focusing on the most promising electric propulsion motor concepts that could be applicable at a large scale within a short period in electric road transport applications (i.e. electric vehicles, HEVs and e-bikes).

In this paper we first estimate the demand for permanent magnets for reaching the global deployment targets for electric vehicles in 2020 and describe its link to material resources availability. The competition for PM-based traction motors from other applications, in particular HEVs and e-bikes, is also evaluated. Then we analyse in-depth the possible substitutes for rare earths-based traction motors and assess their ability to enter into serial production in the short-term (2020). Finally, we evaluate the impact of substitution on reducing the demand for rare earths in electric traction motors under different scenarios.

2. Sources and approach

The research was carried out during 2015–2016 based on information collected from a wide variety of sources, including academic articles, relevant documents and reports on critical raw materials, industry publications, etc. Although an exhaustive survey on the most recent industrial developments is difficult to carry out because of the high level of confidentiality in automotive industries research, this paper integrates the best available information with additional information gathered from interviews with material scientists, technical experts from industry and academics. Over ten interviews have been conducted with European automakers (e.g. Daimler, BMW, etc.) and research project consortium (e.g. MotorBrain, CRM_Innonet, etc.) inquiring about their concerns on rare earths supply and feasibility of substitution of

permanent magnet or rare earths in electric traction motors. In most of the cases the experts asked to remain anonymous.

The demand for rare earths in these applications was estimated using the average amount of permanent magnets in different types of electric powertrains and based on the elemental composition of NdFeB magnets. The deployment targets for EVs are those presented by the International Energy Agency (IEA). Other scenarios were used as complementary information and are referenced throughout the paper. Our demand projections for permanent magnets and rare earths represent a baseline necessary to carry out a more in-depth substitution analysis.

From our analysis and interviews with experts it is clear that magnet producers and automotive industries have looked at different types of substitution, some of them being more prevalent than others. Four main approaches to reduce the demand for rare earths are evaluated in this paper: improving material usage through a better material efficiency, dematerialization (using less NdFeB magnet), direct substitution of rare earths in magnet (element-for-element substitution) and adoption of rare earth-free traction motors (defined as component substitution).

The impact of substitution on decreasing the demand for rare earths in three electric transport sectors – EVs, HEVs and e-bikes – was calculated based on assumed scenarios. While the potential of improving material efficiency is estimated according with industry experts, adoption rate of rare earth-free motors and dematerialisation are more arbitrarily chosen in order to highlight in impact of component substitution on decreasing the future demand for rare earths.

3. Estimation of permanent magnets demand in traction motors used in electric road transport applications

3.1. Applications of permanent magnets in electric traction motors

Today, the NdFeB alloy is a high power magnet with the largest sales share in the permanent magnets market [43]. Based on their high energy density NdFeB magnets are widely used in the automotive industry either for electric traction motors or for non-traction electric components such as audio speakers, transmission, electric power steering, electronic sensors, etc. [17]. Since the magnet content is estimated as negligible in non-traction components [44], in this paper we take into account only electric traction motors.

There is a large diversity of electric propulsion systems available today. In general electric vehicles refer to the passenger cars that have an electric motor as the primary source of propulsion using electrical energy from the grid stored in rechargeable batteries [6,45]. The EV group comprises: battery electric vehicles (BEVs), fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs), range-extended electric vehicles (REEVs) and plug-in electric vehicles (PHEVs). Hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) are not part of EV category since the electric motor represents a secondary propulsion source in combination with an internal combustion engine (ICE). In this paper we will refer to the electric vehicle types BEV and PHEV as well as HEV as these three classes are the most common variants and they may make use of NdFeB magnet [46].

Currently most HEVs and EVs (abbreviated as H&EV) use synchronous motors with NdFeB permanent magnets. It is estimated that by 2025 between 90 and 100% of H&EVs sales will be based on this technology [47]. Overall several reasons explain the common use of rare earth-based PSM in H&EVs [41,48,49]:

- The very strong magnetic field of integrated NdFeB magnets allows a light and compact motor design;
- PSMs have a high efficiency since no external power system is needed to induce a magnetic field in the rotor. The magnetic field is provided by permanent magnet whereas other motor concepts require electricity to generate this electric field;
- PSMs supply high torque and can be more easily controlled.

E-bikes represent an additional application for NdFeB-based PSM because of their ability to offer low weight and compact size. Significant growth rates for e-bikes were registered in the recent years, with almost all production and demand concentrated in China [50].

3.2. Estimation of NdFeB magnet demand in electric vehicle types BEV and PHEV

Based on the current technology, a PSM for an electric vehicle needs between 1 and 2 kg NdFeB depending on motor power, car size, model, etc. [44,47]. If all of the EVs (BEV and PHEV) sold worldwide in 2015 (about 550,000 passenger cars) had been produced with NdFeB magnets, then up to 1100 tonnes of NdFeB would have been required. This amount represents just over 1% of the global production of NdFeB magnets, which was estimated to range between 79,000 tonnes [51] and about 80,000 tonnes [52] in 2015. To meet the global deployment target of 7.2 million EV sales in 2020 [5], the number of EVs produced would need to grow progressively on average by approximately 67% compound annual growth rate (CAGR) from 2015 until 2020. Assuming that all 7.2 million EVs will use PSM motors, these would require between 7200 and 14,400 tonnes of NdFeB magnets in 2020. This translates to a significant increase in the annual demand for NdFeB magnets in EVs by up to 14 times in only 5 years (Fig. 1).

Today China dominates the production of NdFeB magnets by 85–90%, the rest being produced in Japan (10%) and in other countries from Europe, the USA, etc. [52]. Their manufacture appears to continue to move to China where access to REEs remains cheapest and most secure [18].

3.3. Market momentum of hybrid vehicles and estimation of NdFeB magnet demand in HEV applications

The number of new H&EVs models significantly increased from 12 to 60 in the period 2010–2014 (Fig. 2). In 2014 hybrid types HEV and PHEV constituted 65% of the new electric models launched. The high market momentum of HEV, and more recently PHEV, reflect consumer preference for no compromises in range compared to BEV, combined with lower fuel consumption compared to conventional ICE vehicles.

The evolution of H&EV penetration rates of these models is very sensitive to several factors, such as the price of oil, the cost and efficiency of the battery-pack, regulations, government support, infrastructure, customer preferences, etc. An additional factor that could potentially influence the future adoption of electric and hybrid vehicles derives from the availability of rare earths and downstream products (e.g. NdFeB magnet). It is estimated that all HEV and PHEV commercialised

Fig. 1. Evolution of global annual sales of electric vehicles (BEV and PHEV) since 2010 [4] and 2020 deployment target [5]. Estimation of NdFeB demand is based on the assumption that all EVs use NdFeB-PSM technology. The error bar represents the standard error calculated based on the minimum and maximum amount of NdFeB magnet used in a PSM.

Fig. 2. Estimation of new electric vehicles and HEVs models released since 2010 [6].

today use PSM [41,47], thus competing with BEV and other technologies for the same materials. The compact size and high performance of PSM makes it the favoured technology for hybrid cars because manufacturers have to cope with space restrictions due to the need to integrate two drive trains into the car (the electric engine and the combustion engine).

According to Navigant Research, approximately 2.1 million HEVs were sold globally in 2015 [53], mostly in Japan, followed by the USA and Europe [54,55]. Global annual HEVs sales are expected to increase, reaching 2.8 million in 2020 under a conservative scenario [53] or over 3.5 million in a more optimistic one [52]. Further in our analysis we take into account the average of 3.15 million HEVs sales in 2020.

An HEV propulsion motor needs less PM material than an EV motor, circa 42% of the EV-motor magnet weight [56]. This translates to a range of 0.42–0.84 kg magnet per HEV. Under this assumption up to 1800 tonnes NdFeB have been used to produce 2.1 million HEVs in 2015, representing a small fraction (2.3%) of current global production (Fig. 3).

The market trends indicate that HEV models will still remain the dominant electric powertrain in the near future [57]. Based on our projections, the demand for NdFeB in the global HEV market is not expected to see very significant growth levels in the short-term. Up to 2650 tonnes of NdFeB would be required for the 3.15 million HEV, about 1.5 times more compared to 2015.

Fig. 3. Evolution of global annual HEV sales, 2020 forecast [53–55] and estimation of the NdFeB demand for HEV. The error bar represents the standard error calculated based on the minimum and maximum amount of NdFeB magnet used in a PSM.

3.4. Estimation of NdFeB magnet demand in e-bikes

E-bikes integrate a small electric motor and rechargeable batteries to assist the rider in pedalling. In general, they are classified as bicycles given their ability to be pedalled, distinguishing them from electric scooters and motorcycles. Most e-bikes use PSMs with an NdFeB magnet, either as hub motors (integrated in the front or rear wheel) or as mid-drive motors (near the bottom bracket). The amount of NdFeB magnet in an e-bike is estimated to range from 60 g to 350 g up to 100 °C, it needs a low share of dysprosium to withstand demagnetisation. According to experts, the loading of dysprosium in NdFeB magnet for e-bikes application is around 1% Dy, much lower compared to 4% found by Hoenderdaal et al. [59] for two-wheel vehicles, which include along e-bikes also electric scooters and electric motorcycles [59]. This difference might be also somewhat a result of manufacturer efforts to improve efficiency in materials use. Later in this analysis we take into account a conservative loading of 1% Dy in NdFeB magnet for e-bikes.

The global e-bike sales are much higher than current sales of H&EV. It is indicated that about 40 million e-bikes were sold globally in 2013, with China being the biggest market, followed by Europe, Japan and the USA (Fig. 4) [50].

Due to a high saturation of ownership a slower growth was registered in the e-bike sector during the period 2013–2015 [50,52]. But the global e-bike market is expected to increase further at a CAGR of over 4% until 2019 [60]. Based on these data, we estimate that around 50 million e-bikes will be sold in 2020. On the assumption that the e-bikes sold in 2015 is similar to that in 2013 and all e-bikes have used an NdFeB-based PSM, circa 2400–14,000 tonnes of NdFeB would have been required in 2015. The maximum amount represents more than 17% of current global NdFeB production and is approximately 13 times higher than the quantity requested for EVs in the same year. In 2020 the demand for NdFeB in the e-bikes sector is expected to increase up to 17,500 tonnes using current technology.

When adding the NdFeB amounts used in the three sectors – EVs, HEVs and e-bikes – the total annual demand for NdFeB magnet in 2015 could range from about 4000 tonnes in the lower bound case and up to 16,900 tonnes in the upper bound case. The upper and lower bound cases indicate the maximum and minimum masses of NdFeB magnet needed in an e-bike motor. The maximum amount of NdFeB requested for these three sectors represents about 21% of the current global production.

More importantly, the NdFeB demand for these electric road transport applications could increase very rapidly in the next 5 years, driven by EV deployment targets (Fig. 5). To meet the global deployment target of 7.2 million in 2020, the NdFeB demand is estimated to increase by around 1200% between 2015 and 2020. For HEV and e-bikes this increase is much less compared to EV, for instance by 50% and 25%, respectively.

Fig. 4. Estimated e-bikes sales by country in 2013 in million units [50].

Fig. 5. Estimation of global annual demand for NdFeB magnet in EV, HEV and e-bike applications in 2015 and 2020 and the percentage increase assuming that all traction motors are based on NdFeB-PSM technology. Bars correspond to average values. The error bar represents the standard error calculated based on the minimum and maximum amount of NdFeB magnet used in PSM for each application.

In 2020, about 11,500–34,500 tonnes NdFeB magnet might be requested globally for the electric road transport applications. In the upper bound case the NdFeB amount corresponds to a share of over 43% of the current global NdFeB supply. When taking into account the forecasted production of NdFeB magnet in 2020, such as 118,000 tonnes [52], this share decreases to about 30%, but still a very significant fraction of the supply.

3.5. Supply issues for rare earths and their demand for electric road transport applications (HEVs and e-bikes)

The global growth rate of NdFeB consumption for high-tech applications (e.g. hard disk drives) and other energy-related devices (e.g. wind turbines) is likely to increase in the near future [52], thus competing with NdFeB and its constituent rare earths for electric road transport applications. These trends highlight that the REE supply issue must remain high on the agenda of security of supply policies despite recent positive developments such as the lifting China's export bans and decreasing rare earth prices. Other factors to be considered are that the rare earths market is still small and dominated by Chinese production and Chinese demand. Thus it may become again susceptible to price fluctuation.

In 2014 the global annual production of rare earths (in metal form) was estimated to be around 21,000 tonnes Nd, 6300 tonnes Pr and 1400 tonnes Dy [61]. The NdFeB magnet is the major application for all three rare earths [61].

The composition of NdFeB magnet is presented in Table 1.

For applications with a shorter operating period (e.g. in speakers, computer devices, etc.) the NdFeB permanent magnet is ideal. However, for applications like electric traction motors, which have longer

operating times and generate significant amounts of heat, NdFeB is less suitable due to its reduced coercivity. In fact, at temperatures above 80–120 °C, the coercivity of NdFeB declines significantly. Both dysprosium and terbium can be used as a dopant to enhance the coercive force of an NdFeB magnet and enable it to perform stably at higher temperatures. Currently, dysprosium is the most convenient dopant because of its low price compared to terbium. The dysprosium loading in an NdFeB magnet for electric vehicle can vary between 3.7 and 8.7% [59,63], and the resulting compound demonstrates an increased coercivity between 100 and 200 °C. For practical reasons however the content of dysprosium in NdFeB magnet used in electric vehicle motor is kept high, up to 7.7% [59]. According to experts the actual Dy share in NdFeB magnet for an electric traction motor in EV is around 7.5%.

Taking into account the fraction of rare earths in magnet composition (i.e. 30% Nd/Pr (Nd:Pr = 4:1) and 7.5% Dy in H&EVs (or 1% Dy in e-bikes)) and NdFeB demand projected in the previous sections, about 920–4050 tonnes Nd, 230–1010 tonnes Pr and 130–355 tonnes Dy would have been required to satisfy the HEVs, EVs and e-bikes market in 2015. In terms of demand/production share, the three sectors combined accounted for up to 19% Nd, 16% Pr and 25% Dy of each individual rare earth produced in 2014. The overall supply of rare earths is forecasted to increase by a factor of 1.38 from 2014 to 2020 [52]. Assuming that the share of neodymium, praseodymium and dysprosium remains the same with respect to the overall REE supply in 2014, then the global annual supply for these three elements will reach approximately 29,100 tonnes Nd, 8725 tonnes praseodymium and 1940 tonnes Dy in 2020.

If the composition of NdFeB will remain constant, the demand for rare earths in 2020 in these three sectors will increase to a range of 2770–8290 tonnes Nd, 690–2075 tonnes Pr and 670–1450 tonnes Dy. The maximum demand/supply share in 2020 is projected to be about 28% for Nd, 24% for Pr and 75% for Dy. It becomes evident that the highest pressure in terms of material supply is expected for dysprosium. In particular, up to 56% of the estimated annual Dy supply in 2020 (today it is around 6%) would be needed to meet the deployment targets for electric vehicles in 2020. This share is estimated at about 12% for Nd and Pr.

Despite the fact that the production of rare earths and downstream products will increase in the future, however the issue about REE supply and price stability could re-emerge, thus posing a potential bottleneck to the deployment targets for electric vehicles for 2020 and beyond. Opening a new primary production of rare earths is unrealistic in a short time (about 8–10 years elapse between the discovery of rare earths deposits and production at the mine). Mining and refining of REE are associated with serious environmental problems, such as soil and water contamination, human health, air pollution, etc. The environmental impact might also affect a sustainable production and stable supply chain of rare earths. Moreover, large volumes of secondary rare earths production are not expected in the short term to influence the demand/supply balance since many end-of-life products containing NdFeB magnet will enter the recycling circuit after many years [59].

The spike in prices for rare earths during 2011–2012 and the perceived risk associated with their supply and environmental pressure have already led to investments in NdFeB-free motors and the adoption of alternatives. Such technologies can either use PM with a reduced level of rare earths or replace the entire NdFeB-based component with other types of drive system, such as an asynchronous motor. Alternative electric traction motors that do not require rare earths-based magnets have already been developed for serial production by several companies. The main reason for developing REE-free motors was security of supply concerns rather than the price volatility of rare earths [52]. In the next section we evaluate the substitution paths for NdFeB-based synchronous motors used in electric powertrains and analyse their current technology status.

Table 1

Typical composition of sintered NdFeB for applications at room temperature [62].

Chemical element	Percentage by weight
Neodymium (Nd) and/or praseodymium (Pr)	29–32
Iron (Fe)	64.2–68.5
Boron (B)	1.0–1.2
Aluminium (Al)	0.2–0.4
Niobium (Nb)	0.5–1
Dysprosium (Dy)* and/or terbium (Tb)	0.8–1.2

* The Dy content could be increased up to 9% to allow the magnet to operate at high temperatures, i.e. up to 200 °C.

4. Substitution opportunities of rare earths in electric traction motors

4.1. Rare earths substitution in NdFeB magnets and improved material efficiency

At the moment there is no alternative magnet with similar properties to NdFeB or an approach that would enable the full substitution of rare earths with less critical raw materials at large. Such solutions may still not be available in the near future. Currently, research focuses mostly on reducing the rare earth content through two main approaches: (i) increasing material efficiency in magnet production (e.g. grain boundary diffusion processes), thus obtaining NdFeB magnets with less rare earth content but with similar performance; (ii) optimising the motor design, enabling high technical performance while using less NdFeB magnet.

Details about improving material efficiency and rare earths substitution in permanent magnets were already described by our group in the context of NdFeB application in wind turbines [64]. In summary, current research indicates a possible reduction of the amount of Nd and Pr needed to produce NdFeB. For example, Laca-Arántegui estimates a rise in material efficiency for neodymium and praseodymium of up to 29% from 2015 to 2030 in a permanent magnet of equal magnetic strength and cost [65].

As result of research developments, Daimler indicates that the Dy content in permanent magnets in PHEV and HEV vehicles could significantly drop from 7.5–9% to approximately 5% in 2020 and afterwards to 2.5% [66]. Terbium can replace dysprosium without losing performance, but due to its higher price and a supply criticality issue it is not considered a convenient substitute.

4.2. Reducing the amount of NdFeB magnet in electric traction motor: dematerialisation

From the motor design side, high torque densities can be obtained in optimised PSMs by designing new electrical machines while simultaneously using less NdFeB magnets [67]. BMW developed a hybrid motor using fewer magnetic materials embedded into salient rotor structures. This led to a reduction of the rare earths content (30% to 50% less) in the BMW i3 model compared to other PSM designs [42]. Since these motors provide both magnet and reluctance torques, they are also called 'permanent magnet-assisted reluctance motors' or just 'hybrid motors' [68]. The hybrid motor is similar to the EU co-funded MotorBrain project concept for PSM, which uses ferrite for creating reluctance torque [69].

4.3. Component substitution for PSM traction motors in EVs and HEVs

Currently, most electric vehicles use PSMs with NdFeB magnets. These can be affixed to the rotor's surface (surface magnets) or they can be located in pockets within the rotor (buried magnets). The stator carries windings connected to the power supply to produce a rotating magnetic field. The torque results from the interaction between these different magnetic fields.

Alternatives to NdFeB-PSM exist in serial production for several BEV models. For example, the Tesla S, Mercedes B-Class and Renault Twizy have an asynchronous machine (ASM) and the Renault Zoe and Renault Kangoo use an electrically excited synchronous machine (EESM). However, since hybrid vehicles have stricter requirements for a compact size and temperature stability, the use of PSM motors is the preferred option chosen by most manufacturers of HEV and PHEV.

The ASM and EESM technologies are technically available and have good performance, but they are not applied in serial HEV and PHEV production because of their lower power density and higher weight compared to PSM.

Synchronous machines and ASM operate on different physical principles. In ASM, the torque is obtained by electromagnetic induction from the magnetic field of the stator winding. The AC Power is supplied to the motor stator. Whereas a synchronous motor rotor turns at the same rate as the stator field, an asynchronous motor rotor rotates at a slower speed than the stator. The induction motor stator magnetic field therefore constantly changes relative to the rotor. This induces an opposing current in the rotor. Thus, currents in the rotor windings in turn create magnetic fields in the rotor that react against the stator field. The torque is a result of these different magnet fields. The ASM is also called "induction motor" as it bases on the principal of induction.

Externally excited EESMs only differ from PSMs in their rotor design. The PSM uses a permanent magnet in the rotor, whereas the EESM does not use any magnets. Electrical current from the battery magnetizes the copper windings in the EESM rotor to create an electrical magnet.

Other rare earths-free alternative motors are available and some are in the prototype stage with a high potential for the future serial production of EVs and HEVs. Promising alternatives such as ASM with high revolution per minute (rpm) and PSM with low-cost magnets (e.g. ferrite materials) have the potential to enter into the market for EVs and HEVs. Another substitute for PSM might be the switched reluctance motor (SRM) if R&D can successfully solve significant technical obstacles such as inverter incompatibility for other engines and high noise due to very small sound-emitting air gaps.

The current status, major advantages and disadvantages of the most promising motor concepts as well as an outlook to 2020 are given in Table 2.

A crucial point in developing an electric vehicle is the improvement of overall vehicle efficiency to allow longer operational ranges. This means that the efficiency of powertrain designs and their embedded motors is a major issue for vehicle manufacturers. Therefore, alternative motor types have to compete with highly efficient PSMs. The comparison shown in Table 2 indicates that there is not an optimum substitute for PSM that can satisfy all traction conditions while also fulfilling technical and commercial requirements. For instance, compared to PSM, the ASM is less efficient in urban conditions, but more efficient on motorways with high speed. This characteristic is a strong advantage for PSM and EESM types, making them more suitable for urban applications. Other characteristics of the main technologies - PSM, ASM and EESM are shown in Table 3.

The industry aims at a higher driving range for EVs, which also require a high efficiency at high speed. Other motor types such as the switched reluctance machine (SRM) and transverse flux machine (TFM) are in early stage of development and further research is necessary prior to serial production.

The experts interviewed within this study believe that different electric motor concepts will contribute to the future H&EV market. This observation is confirmed by a survey conducted by Hornick [80]. Manufacturers will favour a motor type that best meets the specific needs of the vehicle at reasonable cost-effectiveness. The ferrite magnet-based motor and switched reluctance motor are potential candidates as these technologies may offer the lowest cost in car manufacture compared to the relative high cost of NdFeB magnet-based PSM [42]. Since technical requirements vary with vehicle type and its area of application, a variety of electric traction motors with specific performance characteristics is needed for the development of efficient and competitive H&EVs.

The development time of a new electric motor for H&EVs highly depends on economic conditions. Based on the MotorBrain project, which developed a new motor prototype in three years [69], we could estimate that about 5 years are needed from the conceptual stage until serial production. The time could significantly decrease if electric motor design has merely to be adapted from other similar applications. Given the variety of prototypes available today, it is expected that a rare earth-free motor can be produced within a short time.

Table 2
Overview of main component substitutes for PSM in EVs and HEVs, and comparison to current state-of-the art PSM.

Motor type	Rare earths content	Current status	Major advantages	Major disadvantages	Outlook 2020	Ref.
Permanent synchronous motor (PSM)	0.56 kg REEs per EV motor* (less in HEV and e-bikes)	Used in all serial HEV and in most serial PHEV and BEV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High efficiency at low and medium speeds • Compact size/high power density • Wide dissemination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dependency on rare-earth supply and their price variation • Lower efficiency at high speed 	Maintains a key role in EV and HEV as long as the price of rare earths do not increase significantly	[41,48,49]
Asynchronous motor (ASM)	Rare earths free	Used in some serial BEV (e.g. Tesla S, Mercedes B class, Renault Twizy) and PHEV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low production costs • Robustness • High reliability • High efficiency at high speed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower efficiency than PSM in urban conditions • Lower power density than PSM, requiring more package space and weight • Higher copper demand than PSM 	Maintains serial application in some EV and in mild hybrids, partly as improved ASM with high rpm	[70,71]
Externally excited synchronous motor (EESM)	Rare earths free	Used in few serial BEV (e.g. Renault Zoe) and PHEV Also available for HEV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High efficiency in all speed ranges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower power density than PSM • More package space needed • Complex structure resulting in high manufacturing costs 	Remains an efficient alternative to PSM, but application in HEV is unlikely	[42,72]
ASM with high rpm	Rare earths free	Serial production announced	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential for high energy and material efficiency • Potential for low production costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No experience in serial production yet 	Offers high potential for serial production in BEV, HEV and PHEV due to high efficiency and good cost effectiveness	[42,73]
PSM with low-cost magnets	Rare earths free	Prototypes using ferrite or AlNiCo magnets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential for good overall performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No experience in serial production 	Offers good potential for serial production due to high technical performance and reasonable cost effectiveness	[68,74–76]
Switched reluctance motor (SRM)	Rare earths free	First prototype	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust construction • Potential for cheap engine production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High noise level • Requirement for a specific inverter, which is not compatible to production lines of power electronics for other engines 	Needs further R&D to achieve highly efficient and silent engines suitable for serial production	[41,77]
Transversal flux motor (TFM)	Rare earths free	Early R&D stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential for high power density and efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low technology readiness level 	Might offer high power density and high efficiency, but needs more intense R&D	[78,79]
Hybrid motor (e.g. combine synchronous reluctance principle with permanent excitation)	0.37 kg** REEs or less per motor	Used in the BEV BMW i3 and PHEV BMW 7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Similar performance as PSM with less rare earths 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remaining rare earth demand 	Applied in serial BMW i3 and BMW 7 PHEV production with high potential for further vehicle types and models	[68,69]

* The rare earths content in PSM takes into consideration the range of 1–2 kg permanent magnet per EV traction motor and the following chemical composition of NdFeB: 30% Nd/Pr (Nd:Pr = 4:1) and 7.5% Dy.

** Value relates to 1 kg NdFeB magnet per traction motor with the same chemical composition as above.

Table 3
Comparison of principal characteristics of PSM, ASM and EESM [78].

	PSM	ASM	EESM
Construction space	++	+	+
Weight	++	+	+
Cooling	++	+	O
Production costs	+	++	+
Power density	++	+	+
Reliability	+	++	+
Noise	+	+	+

++ very good performance; + good performance; O low performance.

There are no alternatives to PSM for e-bikes available on a large production scale. Since the current, low rare earth prices give no incentive to manufacturers to develop rare earth-free motors for e-bikes, it seems that industry does not look for alternative solutions that might be accompanied by efficiency losses or higher e-bike weight. This assumption is confirmed by industry experts. Several European manufacturers, e.g. Bosch, Brose Antriebstechnik, Derby Cycle located in Germany and Accell Group from the Netherlands, supply high-quality e-bikes to customers who demand high energy efficiency and light powertrains. Consequently, the competitiveness of these manufacturers highly relies on the production of premium products. Future shortages or high prices of rare earths might be tackled by the fast development of alternative motor systems. This is evident in e-bike motors that have mostly been derived from automotive applications like electric power steering or windshield wiper motors.

5. Impact of substitution on short-term demand for critical rare earths – Nd, Pr and Dy – in H&EV and e-bike applications

Future developments in material efficiency, motor design and component substitution may make the challenge associated with rare earths supply and environmental issue less daunting. There are expected improvements in terms of efficiency in rare earths usage for production of NdFeB magnets. Although the full substitution of rare earths will probably not take place over the coming years, experts consider that the share of Nd and Pr in NdFeB composition may decrease down to 26.5% Nd/Pr from 30% by 2020. Furthermore, a significant drop from 7.5% down to approximately 5% of the Dy content in NdFeB magnets looks to be feasible for PHEVs and HEVs. An optimised PSM design could lead to the use of much less NdFeB magnets (i.e. as in the case of the hybrid design used in BMW's i3 motor). Moreover, some manufacturers may continue with or switch to rare earths-free motors for BEVs. There are also pilot concepts of REEs-free motors for hybrid vehicles (PHEV and HEV) with a high potential for commercialisation.

Due to the large number of parameters and the high uncertainty of future technological and economic developments, the precise future

penetration rate of substitutions remains unclear. Current low prices and a sufficient supply of rare earths give no strong incentive to switch to rare earth-free motors, unless they become more cost and performance-effective. In this context, experts see a high potential for the newly developed ASM with high rpm, which has high efficiency and could also achieve low production costs.

Based on possible technological developments and inputs received from experts, in this paper we have analysed different substitution scenarios along three main parameters: materials efficiency, dematerialisation (less NdFeB content) and component substitution (replacement of PSM by other rare earth-free technology). We grouped them in 4 case scenarios: (i) *substitution case A*, takes into account an increase in material efficiency; (ii) *substitution case B*, considers the material efficiency of case A and 30% of component substitution; (iii) *substitution case C*, on top of the material efficiency of case A it assumes 50% component substitution, and (iv) *substitution case D* adds dematerialization (i.e. 40% less NdFeB magnet on top of case C. Table 4 gives an overview on the assumptions of the four substitution scenarios and compares them to the reference scenario, which exhibits no substitution and features the same NdFeB demand as shown in Fig. 5.

The results obtained from this analysis are presented in Fig. 6.

The impact of substitution is revealed through the four different scenarios A, B, C and D. The results show that substitution has the potential to reduce the short-term global demand for rare earths in the H&EV and e-bikes sectors. Compared to the 2020 reference case a decreasing demand by 12% for Nd and Pr can be achieved by improving material efficiency (substitution case A). This reduction can be more significant (from 38% up to 56%) if an adoption of alternative components complement the material efficiency (e.g. 30% or 50% of PSM technology are replaced by rare earth-free electric traction motors as evidenced in substitution case B and C, respectively). If the decrease of NdFeB amount (through dematerialisation) will also take place, the reduction in Nd and Pr demand can reach about 73% (substitution case D).

In case of Dy a substantial demand reduction (up to 33%) in H&EVs can be reached just by improving material efficiency, such as by decreasing the Dy loading in the magnet from 7.5% to 5%. A decreasing of Dy loading below 5% in NdFeB used in electric traction motors for serial production of electric and hybrid vehicles will likely not take place before 2020. Material efficiency has no impact on e-bikes, which already use a very small loading (1% Dy). Moreover, if 30% of the rare earths' components is replaced, the demand for Dy in electric vehicles could be reduced by half (substitution case C) with respect to the 2020 reference case, decreasing further by 80% in case of substitution case D.

While already in the case of substitution case B the demand for rare earths in 2020 might decrease below the 2015 level in HEV and e-bikes, however even in the most ambitious substitution scenario (D) the growth rate for Nd, Pr and Dy consumption in electric vehicle sector is expected to increase over the next 5 years in order to meet the

Table 4
Possible substitution scenarios for rare earths in PSM used in H&EV and e-bikes.

Substitution scenario - 2020	Material efficiency		Dematerialisation	Component substitution (%)
	Nd/Pr loading* in PM (%)	Dy loading** in PM (H&EVs) (%)		
Base year - 2015	30	7.5	0	0
Reference case (no substitution)	30	7.5	0	0
Substitution case A (material efficiency)	26.5	5	0	0
Substitution case B (material efficiency + low component substitution)	26.5	5	0	30
Substitution case C (material efficiency + high component substitution)	26.5	5	0	50
Substitution case D (material efficiency + high component substitution + dematerialisation)	26.5	5	Reduction of NdFeB amount by 40%***	50

* Nd and Pr are found in ratio 4:1.

** Dy loading in e-bikes is considered 1% in all cases.

*** 40% magnet reduction leads to 0.6–1.5 kg NdFeB/electric car and 36–210 g NdFeB/e-bike.

Fig. 6. Estimation of global annual demand for Nd, Pr and Dy in 2015 and 2020 in electric traction motors for H&EVs and e-bikes under different substitution scenarios. Bars correspond to average values. The error bar represents the standard error calculated based on the minimum and maximum amount of NdFeB magnet used in PSM for each application.

deployment targets set for 2020. This demand is estimated to be at least 3 times more in case of the substitution case D, compared to over 13% in the reference scenario without any substitution.

The growing demand for rare earths indicates a need for further actions to ensure a secure supply and development of suitable alternatives for rare earths-based PM traction motors. This will allow Europe and other countries to accomplish the overall goals of cutting CO₂ emissions and reducing the transport sector's dependence on oil.

6. Conclusions

Despite the benefits of climate change mitigation and from potential fuel savings, several barriers could hinder the widespread adoption of electric vehicles. Among them is the potential supply disruption of critical rare earths for NdFeB magnet-based electric traction motors. In 2015, the global EV sector consumed around 1% of the total market for NdFeB magnets. Driven by efforts to foster EVs adoption and meet ambitious deployment targets of EVs in 2020, the demand for NdFeB could rapidly and significantly increase over the next few years. HEVs and e-bikes further compete with EVs for NdFeB-based PSM.

We estimate that the H&EV and e-bike sectors combined would require over two times more NdFeB magnets in 2020 compared to 2015 (between 11,500–34,500 tonnes NdFeB), representing up to 30% of expected global NdFeB supply in 2020. Moreover the market for rare earths-based permanent magnets will likely grow for other applications, e.g. high-tech and energy-devices. The overall rising demand for NdFeB magnets could have important implications on the supply chain for rare earth, which may also lead to price fluctuation. Dy poses the highest supply risk as up to 75% of its 2020 supply may be required to meet the global electric road transport applications.

The potential supply risks associated with rare earths for electric road transport applications cannot be easily mitigated as there are no effective substitutes for the rare earths used in permanent magnets. However higher material efficiency, dematerialisation and adoption of alternative components, e.g. rare earths-free electric traction motors, can attenuate the future increasing demand for rare earths. Adoption of different substitution paths should take place in parallel as it does not appear that one substitution method prevails over the others.

Under the most optimistic substitution scenario, which implies adoption of different types of substitution, the global demand in 2020 for H&EV applications could be drastically reduced by 75% for Nd and Pr, and 80% for Dy versus a reference without substitution in the same year. But even if such optimistic scenario was to be successfully implemented, the global annual demand for rare earths in electric traction motors in electric vehicle applications is expected to grow significantly up to 2020. This calls for an integrated 'security-of-supply' policy that need to consider various strategies along secure access, recycling and substitution. For Europe and other countries/regions that lack domestic supplies, substitution may be an effective short-term solution. This paper reveals that a number of high potential options for PMS exist and they could be rapidly brought to commercialisation, should prices for rare earths increase. However more R&D investments are needed to further develop these solutions and to search for even better alternatives.

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